

An Annotated Bibliography on Written Corrective Feedback in L2 Settings in Saudi Arabia

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Article Info	Abstract
<i>Article History</i>	<p><i>Learning English became one of the requirements of modern-day life. There are people who learn English as a second/foreign language more than any other language. Teaching English for academic and special purposes became major academic disciplines in most higher education institutions across the world. Writing in English is an essential skill that ESL/EFL learners need to practice and improve to promote their English language proficiency. The majority of L2 learners have faced various difficulties when approaching writing tasks. Providing learners with written corrective feedback on their drafts has been adopted as a necessary classroom practice. Many researchers have addressed various aspects and different issues related to WCF and reported inconsistent and sometimes contrasting results. This annotated bibliography is designed to assist researchers working on WCF in second/foreign language settings and to provide language teachers with a solid theoretical and pedagogical background based on data of many types to enhance their teaching. Teachers had different beliefs on the significance and nature of the provided corrections and multiple practices related to the quality, quantity, and methods of responding to students' writings. Also, learners had different preferences with respect to receiving teachers' feedback and expressed several complaints against various shortcomings regarding the provided comments. The current work is by no means exhaustive, but an attempt to give an overview of the field and highlight published studies written on a variety of topics related to written corrective feedback in the context of teaching English as a foreign language in Saudi Arabia.</i></p>
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Introduction

This is a meta-analysis investigating ten quasi-experimental studies of written corrective feedback. The study concluded that written corrective feedback cannot be taken as a conclusive predictor of the improvement of students' writing proficiency over time. The focus of teachers' comments is the real indicator to determine the efficacy of the feedback. In most of the cases, students benefit more from focused corrective feedback while unfocused comments (comprehensive WCF) could have harmful effects on students' writing over time. In particular, responding to many types of errors makes learners unable to figure out they have been corrected and consequently cannot process the corrective feedback successfully. Therefore, writing teachers should select a limited number of error to respond to and make certain corrections based on the learners' needs for written corrective feedback. Providing focused corrective feedback is useful for students to notice errors and monitor their own progress. Also, writing teachers should explain the different rules and give examples to make sure students understand various structural and content aspects.

Abdelrahman, M. A. S. (2016). Teachers' and Students' Preferences for Error Correction in EFL Writing. Doctoral dissertation, Majmaah University, Saudi Arabia.

This Doctoral dissertation examined the attitudes of 50 teachers and 100 students in the preparatory year at Majmaah University towards error correction in writing of classroom. They responded to two surveys separately to elicit their perceptions and preferences of the ways of error correction. Findings showed that teachers and students have common preferences and positive tendency for corrective feedback in the sense that it is an effective tool to help students improve their writing. Students preferred to get comprehensive WCF through which their teachers mark and correct all writing errors and thought that providing feedback is one of the basic responsibilities of writing teachers. Teachers, conversely, believed that the provision of excessive written corrective feedback consumes too much time and makes students depend heavily on their teachers for correcting errors. They favored to focus on certain errors which are more important and leave simple errors for students to

edit. They also thought that giving feedback at early stages is more beneficial to students to help them understand the concept and function of corrective feedback.

Alamri, H. R. H. (2018). Examining the Perceptions and Preferences of Saudi EFL Student Teachers Concerning Teachers' Feedback Practices. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 8(18), 48-67.

The participants in this study were thirty-one Saudi female EFL student teachers at the College of Education at Taibah University. Their perceptions of the importance of and evaluation of teacher feedback practices were examined. Also, their preferences for different types of error correction and the mechanism of providing WCF were investigated. Quantitative data were collected via three 5-point Likert scale questionnaires. Findings revealed that most of the participants had positive attitudes towards the different methods of providing corrective feedback and preferred WCF as a supporting tool to gain more knowledge about how to write better. The participants also highlighted the value of teacher feedback to improve their writing abilities and emphasized the need for one-on-one conferences with their teachers to discuss their comments. Such concentrated sessions of feedback discussion encourages the creation of a positive educational atmosphere and real cooperative language learning settings which could positively reinforce the learners' desire for more active learning. Student teachers also highlighted the importance of authentic high quality corrective feedback to meet the learners' various needs and expectations. Such structured help from teachers has positive effects on students to build up their academic experience and develop their sense of awareness and responsibility.

Albelihi, H. H. (2022). Written corrective feedback: A comparative study of the preferences and beliefs of EFL teachers and learners in Saudi Arabia. *F1000Research*, 11, 452-464.

In this study the researcher surveyed the perceptions and preferences of 92 EFL learners from Qassim University, Saudi Arabia, towards the different types of WCF they receive from their teachers. The participants responded to a questionnaire comprised 11 close-ended items. Results showed that they believed in the benefit of WCF and thought teacher response is necessary for them to improve their writing. They also preferred to receive direct comments, especially on grammar, maybe because they thought direct feedback is most appropriate for them to understand their grammatical mistakes. At the same time. The participants preferred coded feedback on content aspects. Also, the real feedback practices and corrective comments of three EFL teachers in two phases were evaluated. Results indicated that the teachers tended to provide more direct comments to students on grammar, vocabulary, and content which indicates that teachers in that setting found explicit correction more effective in treating students' errors and eliciting improvement. The study recommended that researchers should pay more attention to the various difficulties surrounding the scope of feedback.

Albogami, M. (2020). An Inquiry into Effective Written Feedback from EFL Teachers' and Students' Perspectives at a Saudi University. Doctoral dissertation, University of Exeter.

The context of this doctoral dissertation was the Preparatory-Year College (PY) at King Saud University. Mixed methods were employed to investigate L2 teachers' and students' attitudes towards effective written corrective feedback. Quantitative data were collected via a questionnaire administered to 88 L2 teachers from the Preparatory-Year College and 150 L2 male upper-intermediate students in the science track. Qualitative data were gathered using semi-structured interviews with 4 students and 4 teachers. Both teachers and students thought WCF is valuable and important to promote interaction inside classrooms, enhance students' confidence in their abilities, and reinforce learning in general. Both teachers and students considered teacher WCF the best source to improve student writing accuracy. Students expressed preferences to receive feedback on multiple drafts and preferences for positive comments to their writing corrective suggestions that match their English proficiency level. Teachers emphasized the significance of responding to accuracy issues such as grammar, vocabulary, and mechanics as they are problematic and challenging for most of the learners.

Alharbi, S. H. (2016). Effect of teachers' written corrective feedback on Saudi EFL University students' writing achievements. *International Journal of Linguistics*, 8(5), 15-29.

The purpose of this study was to explore how Saudi EFL university students perceived their teachers' corrective feedback and to examine the effect error correction on their writing development. Subjects of the study were 50 male students at the department of English in the College of Languages and Translation at King Saud University. Subjects were randomly selected and distributed into two groups of 25 students each. Students in the experimental group received regular and systematic corrective comments on their writing while students in the control group did not receive any corrective feedback. Instructional procedures took 10 weeks when students took a pretest and a posttest to measure their progress and check how much progress they made with or without WCF provided to their writing. Findings revealed that students in the experiment group developed more and

employed their teacher's comment to avoid a number of errors in their subsequent writing which is considered a considerable encouraging effect on students' writing achievements.

Alharbi, S. H. (2020). Efficacy of different types of written corrective feedback on EFL university students' writing quality. *International Journal of English Linguistics*, 10(4). 217-226.

The researcher in this study explored the predicted effect of three different types of written corrective feedback on student writing quality and also the effect of feedback compared with no feedback on their writing progress. Sixty male English major students at King Saud University participated in the study. They were divided into three groups of 20 students each. Students in experimental group A received direct comments, students in experimental group B received indirect response, while the control group students received minimal written corrective feedback. All the participants took pre and posttests to examine how beneficial corrective comments were on the level of their writing. The findings revealed that there were statistically significant differences in the participants' writing performance in favor of direct WCF in improving their writing quality. The participants also responded to a questionnaire of 22 items to explore their perceptions and attitudes towards teacher corrective feedback. According to the results of the questionnaire, the participants showed positive attitudes towards corrective comments and highlighted that their teachers' written feedback helped them fix different types of errors.

Alharthi, S. (2016). Saudi Female Teachers' and Students' Understanding of the Role and the Importance of Feedback on Writing. *Journal of Research in Curriculum Instruction and Educational Technology*, 2(1), 25-43.

This study involved 100 female Saudi university students at King Abdulaziz University for the purpose of exploring their attitudes towards the role and importance of corrective feedback. At the beginning of the academic year, all students took a placement test and based on their grades they were assigned at three different levels: elementary, pre-intermediate, and intermediate. All the participants responded to a 19-item questionnaire revolved around different types and focused on feedback (written, oral, content, organization, grammar, mechanics, and vocabulary, among others). Results of the questionnaire indicated that students attached high importance to teachers' corrective comments more than feedback from their peers. Students also preferred direct types of teachers' feedback, where errors were underlined or circled and corrected, over other indirect types of comments. Elementary and intermediate level students appeared considered feedback on grammatical errors very helpful while students in the pre-intermediate level preferred feedback on spelling errors. The study recommended that teachers should provide various types of feedback depending on students' perspectives and needs.

Al-Hazzani, N., & Altalhab, S. (2018). Can Explicit Written Corrective Feedback Develop Grammatical and Lexical Accuracy of Saudi EFL Learners? *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*, 6(4), 16-24.

This study extended over a 10-week period to examine the reactions of 50 female foundation level students towards written corrective feedback. Data were collected via a pre-/post-test/delayed post-test to compare the performance of subjects in an experimental group (29 students) and a control group (21 students). The researchers wanted to assess how helpful teachers' comments were on the level of students' written essays and how far WCF affected their written lexical and grammatical accuracy. The results indicated that subjects in the experimental group made significant progress and achieved better writing performance than their counterparts in the control group. In particular, there were statistically significant differences between the performance scores of subjects in the post-test in favor of those in the experimental group. Test results revealed also that subjects in the experimental group made fewer lexical errors which reflected the significance of corrective feedback in improving students' vocabulary use. In addition, students' use of various grammatical aspect improved in the post-test especially with respect to how to use prepositions, nouns, verbs, and articles.

Aljasir, N. (2021). Matches or Mismatches? Exploring Shifts in Individuals' Beliefs About Written Corrective Feedback as Students and Teachers-to-be. *Journal of Teaching and Teacher Education*, 9(1), 1-10.

The aim of this study was examining the relationship between students' and teachers' beliefs regarding WCF and their real practices. Qualitative data were gathered through different stages. First, 52 participants (28 females and 24 males) wrote a descriptive essay in English about their role models and corrective comments were provided to them during semi-structured interviews to elicit their beliefs about WCF. Then the same participants, who were teachers-to-be by that time were requested to comment on a descriptive essay to observe how their beliefs were reflected in their actual WCF practice. The findings indicated that most of the participants expressed positive attitudes towards corrective feedback and that their beliefs and WCF practices

were consistent to a great extent. In particular, the participants, as students, preferred global, unfocused, and indirect corrective comments, and as teachers-to-be, they endorsed giving global, focused and both direct and indirect WCF. The participants' actual responses provided to the descriptive essay showed that most of their WCF practices accorded with their beliefs and preferences.

Alkhatib, N. (2015). Written corrective feedback at a Saudi university: English language teachers' beliefs, students' preferences, and teachers' practices. Doctoral dissertation, University of Essex.

This PhD dissertation explored the beliefs of 10 L2 writing teachers with regard to written corrective feedback (WCF) and how their classroom practices aligned/misaligned with their expressed beliefs. Also, the preferences and reactions of 45 Saudi L2 students towards WCF were examined. The methods of data collection included a questionnaire completed by the students on their WCF preferences, interviews with the teachers to investigate their WCF beliefs and classroom observation to examine teachers' implementation of different aspects of WCF. The findings revealed that the teachers gave more WCF on mechanics and tended to use the comprehensive/indirect approach of providing corrective comments. These practices did not correspond to the teachers' beliefs of focusing WCF on vocabulary and grammar or responding to students' writing based on their level of proficiency. In addition, teachers' practices did not accord with students' preferences to receive direct WCF and get more comments on grammar. The source of incongruence between teachers' beliefs and practices, based on the interviews data, was the insufficient awareness about the nature and significance of corrective feedback. Also, there were various contextual factors that prevented teachers from discussing the use of WCF with their students.

Alqurashi, F. (2015). Perspectives of Saudi EFL learners towards teacher response in writing courses. *International Journal of English Linguistics*, 5(5), 37-46.

The perspectives of 86 Saudi EFL freshmen were investigated in relation to their teachers' corrective feedback to their writing. Subjects responded to a questionnaire to explore the factors that influenced their preferences and attitudes about WCF when they write in English as a foreign language. The results showed that the students considered teacher written comments important and represented a great help to develop the necessary writing skills needed to improve their composing abilities. Teacher response on both surface-level errors and meaning-level errors helped students to gain confidence in themselves as good writers especially when they produced better writing with less mistakes. The subjects also stressed the importance of all types of corrective comments and mentioned they thought carefully about all the corrections that their teachers provided. These responses indicate positive attitudes towards written corrective feedback. The study concluded with a recommendation for improving teaching conditions and reducing the number of students in writing classes which could be motivating for teachers to avoid over-stressing the error correction and provide focused and clear response

Al-Saleh, N. A. (2018). The Impact of Positive and Corrective Feedback via Showbie on Saudi Students' English Writing. *Arab World English Journal: Thesis Collection*, 1-121.

This MA thesis examined the impact of computer-mediated corrective feedback on the writing level of 24 EFL Saudi female students. The researcher assessed the participants' attitudes towards teacher comments when receiving computer-mediated corrections via a learning management system called Showbie. Also, written corrective feedback strategies were investigated in relation to their positive impact on the students' performance when they write in English. Two research instruments were used to collect data: a questionnaire and pre- and post- essay writing tests. The participants were divided into two experimental groups of 12 students each. Students in the first group received direct electronic CF while students in the second group received metalinguistic electronic CF. The study found that there were statistically significant differences between students in the two groups in the writing performance indicating that students made use of direct corrective feedback to avoid different errors. Moreover, all the participants enjoyed receiving computer-mediated positive and corrective feedback via Showbie. L2 Saudi female learners had different preferences for written corrective feedback. In particular, they did not like indirect corrective responses, but they preferred direct corrective comments and thought they had positive impact on their writing performance.

Alshahrani, N. A. (2020): *Learners' Engagement with Written Corrective Feedback and their L2 Writing Performance*. Doctoral dissertation, University of Leicester.

This is a PhD dissertation investigating the influence of written corrective feedback on L2 Saudi female learners and the improvement of their subsequent writing performance in the target language. The researcher adopted a quasi-experimental design that involved two experimental groups where all the learners received indirect error-

coded corrective comments in two modes: computer-mediated and traditional handwritten. In addition to assessing the effectiveness of employing various modes on the learners' engagement with WCF, the researcher examined the influence of thinking-aloud as a mediating strategy to facilitate learner interaction with instructor's comments within the different modes. The findings showed that learner-centered settings make students interact more with corrective responses, which helps them enhance their performance and promote their knowledge construction. The participants found using electronic tools, such as word processor or online text editing, effective in understanding and implementing corrective feedback. Also, most of the learners complained that not enough time was allocated to discuss their errors, which stresses the significance of teacher-learner conferences to help the learners get the maximum benefit of WCF. Moreover, training sessions are needed to help instructors improve their professional productivity especially with respect to providing constructive feedback.

Alshahrani, A., & Storch, N. (2014). Investigating teachers' written corrective feedback practices in a Saudi EFL context: How do they align with their beliefs, institutional guidelines, and students' preferences? *Australian Review of Applied Linguistics*, 37(2), 101-122.

The aim of this study was exploring the factors that shape the relationship between teachers and students during the process of giving and receiving written corrective feedback and how far teachers' WCF practices align with their beliefs and students' preferences. The population of the study consisted of three teachers and forty five students, 15 students per teacher. In the interviews about their perceptions and beliefs with regard to providing WCF, the three teachers stressed the importance of responding to students' writings as one of the main tasks in their teaching career. The findings from the student questionnaire revealed that all the students valued receiving comments from their teachers and considered them effective in identifying errors and improving their writing. The study found also that although the teachers had to follow strict institutional guidelines in providing comprehensive indirect feedback, they did not seem to be fully aware of the type and focus of their corrective responses. They overlooked errors on mechanics, syntax, and lexis more than those related to the meaning. Also, teachers were generally unaware of their students' preferences and their comments did not always accord with their WCF beliefs.

Alsharif, A. A., & Alyousef, H. S. (2017). Investigating ESL/EFL students' approaches in response to feedback: A case study. *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 13(2), 153-181.

This case study was conducted to explore the reactions of 6 upper-intermediate L2 writers to corrective feedback, how they utilized CF to revise their drafts, the frequent steps in their revision processes, and how teacher comments motivated them to improve their writing. The researchers employed instruments to collect data: the students written texts, the tutors written feedback and structured and retrospective interviews. The results indicated that there were striking differences between the participants in their revision processes. Three of them made more changes on surface-level errors and focused on body comments more than on end comments, their revisions were limited to the provided corrective responses, and they attended to 98%–99 % of them. The other three participants focused on broader meaning-level changes, created multiple changes in their final drafts, attended to only 19%-33 % of the corrective comments which indicates their revisions were self-initiated and not restricted to their teacher's suggestions. The researchers called for updating teaching methods to elevate the level of awareness of the different revision strategies that L2 learners could utilize to enhance their writing proficiency.

Alsuhaibani, Z. (2021). Corrective Feedback Controversies in Language Learning: With a Focus on Direct Written Corrective Feedback. *International Journal of English Language & Translation Studies*, 8(4), 35-43.

The purpose of this paper was examining the effect of direct focused written corrective feedback on the writing abilities of 49 female EFL students. All the participants were first year English students in an age range between 19 and 21 years old. After receiving explicit form-focused instruction on tag questions, conjunctions, quantifiers, and articles, students' writings were assessed in three phases: pre feedback phase, post feedback phase, and delayed test. In each phase, the participants wrote a conversation that includes examples of the grammatical structures. The findings indicated that there were statistically significant differences in students' writings in the pre and post feedback phase in terms of how they made use of direct focused written corrective feedback. Students made less errors in their post feedback drafts which could be taken as a sign in favor of the short-term effect of direct focused written corrective feedback. Nevertheless, there were no significant differences between students' writings in the pre feedback phase and the delayed test which indicates that the participants reached a good level understanding how to use the introduced grammatical structures.

Al-Wossabi, S. A. N. (2019). Corrective feedback in the Saudi EFL writing context: A new perspective. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 9(3), 325-331.

The population of this study were sixty Saudi EFL students enrolled in an English composition class (level 2) and their English language proficiency ranged between beginners and high intermediate. The aim of the study was to investigate the subjects' attitudes towards the way their teacher correct their writing composition in this class especially that the same instructor taught them English composition class (level 1). The participants responded to a 12-item questionnaire to elicit their reaction about the received corrective feedback. The findings revealed that the participants generally valued their teacher's comments and found them helpful to improve their writing. Also, the participants had both positive and negative views towards different practices related to the mechanism of providing corrective feedback. The participants had the opportunity to elaborate on their perceptions through the follow up interviews. In particular, low achieving students found it unfair to be treated like high achievers with respect to time allocated for correcting mistakes. High proficient writers highlighted that they enjoyed editing different types of errors pointed out by their teachers which indicates that the provided corrective feedback enhanced their knowledge of the basic grammatical forms.

Alzahrani, H. F. (2016). Teachers' Stated Beliefs on Coded Unfocused Corrective Feedback in EFL Writing at a Saudi University. *TESOL International Journal*, 11(1), 52-64.

This study surveyed the stated beliefs of ten EFL teachers on coded unfocused corrective feedback and how it could improve the learners' writing accuracy. At the time of the research, the teachers taught at the intensive English language program offered by at King Abdulaziz University. The ten EFL teachers responded to a questionnaire with both closed and open-ended items. The findings indicated that most of the participants believed that coded unfocused corrective feedback is relatively useful in helping learners improve their writing accuracy especially for highly motivated learners who like to employ such feedback to avoid errors. A few participants thought that coded unfocused corrective feedback is not beneficial for most L2 learners in the sense that their errors should be pointed out clearly to those learners to help them make use of the provided comments. Some other participants chose to take a more neutral position and stressed that coded corrective feedback can be an effective tool only if used selectively, not with all types of errors.

Aseeri, F. M. M. (2019). Written Corrective Feedback as Practiced by Instructors of Writing in English at Najran University. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 8(3), 112-121.

The researcher in this study administered a questionnaire to investigate the different methods that ten female faculty members at the department of English language at Najran University employ to provide written corrective feedback. In addition, another questionnaire was administered to examine how far forty female L2 students made use of their teachers' comments. The results showed that most of the teachers preferred to give direct feedback. In particular, they thought that the best methods to help students improve their writing abilities was identifying errors, underlining or circling mistakes, and explaining how to correct such errors. Some teachers also were in favor of using Arabic to provide comments in the sense that feedback might be more understandable if it is provided in the students' mother tongue. The teachers did not prefer to provide indirect feedback where students' errors are underlined or circled without giving any suggestions for correction. The students expressed strong preferences for direct and comprehensive feedback and mentioned they expected from their teachers to identify all the errors in their writings and also give suggestions how they could fix those errors.

Basabrin, A. (2019). Exploring EFL instructors and students perceptions of written corrective feedback on blackboard platform: A case study. *Arab World English Journal: Special Issue: Application of Global ELT Practices in Saudi Arabia* 1. 179-192.

This is a case study that involved a female EFL instructor and three college students at the preparatory year at King Abdulaziz University to explore their preferences and perceptions towards written corrective feedback on the Blackboard platform. Qualitative data were collected via semi-structured interviews to investigate the participants' beliefs on feedback given via the Learning Management System. The instructor stated that she believes that feedback is very effective for students to improve their writing and important as a tool for building students-teacher rapport. She mentioned also that the focus should not be on correcting every single mistake but on providing comments to correct the major errors whether those errors are structural or derived from the writing content. It is important for that instructor to discuss writing errors with students in class because there is no enough time for teacher-student conferences due to the pressure of classes. The three students highlighted the significance of corrective feedback in helping them to fix errors and edit their drafts. Even though the three

students wanted feedback on all errors in their writings, they expressed some kind of frustration to see their drafts full of corrections.

Elboroloy, S. A. (2019). Improving literacy skills of Saudi English Majors through explicit and implicit corrective feedback modes at Shaqra' University. *Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 9(6), 09-16.

This study involved seventy five Saudi female EFL students from the second level at the English department, Shaqra University. The study adopted a quasi- experimental design in which the participants were assigned into three groups, two experimental and one control, of twenty five students each. Students in the experimental groups received corrective feedback in relation to literacy skills while the control group students did not receive any comments. Three instruments of data collection were employed. A questionnaire of 16 items was administered and the results indicated a statistically significant difference in which the participants favored implicit comments rather than explicit responses. In addition, pre and post literacy tests were implemented to assess the benefit and effect of the type of feedback on mastering literacy skills. The results showed that students in the experimental groups utilized corrective feedback and made less errors than those in the control group. Finally, the participants were interviewed to talk about their perceptions and mentioned that they prefer implicit feedback because of special characteristics that make most of them shy and unable to accept overt comments.

Grami, M. (2004). The Effect of Teachers' Written Feedback on ESL Students' Writing: A Study on a Saudi ESL University-Level Context. Doctoral dissertation, University of Essex.

This thesis explored the perceptions and attitudes of Saudi L2 learners towards their teachers' written feedback especially with respect to how far they believe in the efficacy of the received comments. The participants were 40 university-level students at the English department, King Abdul Aziz University. Data were collected via three instruments. The findings of the questionnaire indicated that the participants appreciated their teachers' written feedback and believed that they can improve their writing with the help of the received corrective comments. Most participants preferred direct feedback over indirect responses and appreciated constructive criticism much more than praise. During the semi-structured interviews the participants mentioned that they do not like neither insincere praise, because it is not helpful, nor plain criticism, because it is discouraging. Teachers stressed the significance of providing appropriate feedback to help students overcome a number of difficulties. They highlighted also the importance of responding to a wide variety of errors depending on the degrees of necessity. This shows that both teachers and students were highly motivated to give/receive corrective feedback.

Grami, G. M. A., & Alshenqeeti, H. M. A. (2013). Socio-cultural dimension of students' attitudes towards specific forms of corrective feedback: The case of criticism in written comments. *Journal of Teaching and Education*, 2(2), 155-159.

This paper reports on a project that aimed to investigate L2 learners' perspectives on the different strategies that language teachers employ when responding to students' writings. The project involved 36 male university-level students at the English department, King Abdul Aziz University. The researchers used a structured questionnaire to collect data. All the subjects welcomed their teachers' corrective feedback and considered it important to address all their writing inaccuracies which in turn helps them edit and avoid errors. The majority of students were happy to accept all kinds of comments and accommodate criticism from their teachers. The subjects considered critical responses constructive and justifiable since they help them write better which indicates a high-level enthusiasm to make use of the corrective feedback to improve their level of writing proficiency. The subjects mentioned also that they reduce the impact of teachers' criticism by trying as much as possible to attend to all the corrective comments in order to avoid the typical mistakes.

Halim, T., Wahid, R., & Halim, S. (2021). EFL students' attitudes toward corrective feedback: a study conducted at undergraduate level. *Saudi Journal of Language Studies*, 1(1), 40-49.

Sixty female university-level students were surveyed in this study to examine their attitudes towards online and offline corrective feedback and to explore their preferences in relation to how corrective comments should be presented to meet their needs. The participants, who were from levels 7 and 8 of the English bachelor program at King Khalid University, were enrolled in a class via Blackboard, a learning management system. They responded to questionnaire eight closed items to collect their views. The results showed that the participants had positive attitudes towards corrective feedback and considered their teachers' comments motivating to learn more about the writing process. The participants also endorsed both types of feedbacks, online (immediate/automated)

and offline (delayed), are essential to the participants to improve their writing and enrich their linguistic accuracy. Even though all the participants highlighted the importance of corrective feedback as a beneficial learning tool that enhances their achievements, some participants expressed concerns about recognizing what comments that could help them overcome certain difficulties.

Hamouda, Arafat. (2011). A Study of Students and Teachers' Preferences and Attitudes towards Correction of Classroom Written Errors in Saudi EFL Context. *English Language Teaching*4(3), 128-141.

This study explored the preferences and attitudes of both EFL students and teachers towards written corrective feedback. The participants were 200 native Arabic speakers enrolled in the Preparatory Year Program in addition to 20 English instructors at Qassim University. Students and instructors responded to two different questionnaires to survey their perspectives towards error treatment. All the students valued their teachers' corrective feedback and most of them favored teachers' responses over peer comments even though peer response groups were employed as a basic learning tool in the . Both instructors and students preferred to provide/ receive feedback at all stages of the writing process; in the prewriting, drafting, revising or evaluating. Moreover, the students' preferences did not meet with the instructors' beliefs with regard to various aspects. Most of the surveyed students believed that teachers should correct all errors in their drafts and consider that part of their teachers' job while teachers do not believe in comprehensive feedback and prefer to select certain errors to respond to.

Hussain, M. S., Albeshir, K. B., &Farid, A. (2020). Teachers' Error Treatment Practices and Perceptions in Teaching English to Adult EFL Learners in Saudi Arabia: A Gender-Based Qualitative Study. *Global Regional Review*, 1, 290-299.

The population of this study were twenty four female and thirty six male English teachers at Qassim University. They were interviewed to check their error correction beliefs and practices. Even though the teachers had diverse approaches towards errors, there were no significant differences in the perceptions of male and female participants. Teachers of both genders considered errors to be instrumental, natural to occur, and should be treated sensibly for the purpose of boosting, not breaking, the learners' confidence. They looked at errors as signs of development that need teacher intervention to enhance the students' learning process and promote their pace of progress. However, male and female teachers expressed different opinions regarding sources of errors in different learning activities. Most female participants considered lack of motivation a major cause of errors while most male teachers thought L1 interference can cause more errors. The researchers found a few cases of unthoughtful and irrational error treatment practices such as overcorrecting certain errors, giving blunt comments, or pointing to errors without providing adequate explanation.

Mustafa, R. F. (2012). Feedback on the Feedback: Sociocultural Interpretation of Saudi ESL Learners' Opinions about Writing Feedback. *English Language Teaching*, 5(3), 3-15.

The purpose of this small-scale qualitative study was to analyze the attitudes and opinions of 31 Saudi students towards their teachers' written corrective feedback and their perceptions on what constitutes helpful feedback. The participants were enrolled in a private ESL school in Vancouver, Canada. Data were collected via informal conversational interviews and semi-structured open-ended question interviews. The findings indicated that the participants did not believe that the feedback they receive had a positive impact on their writing abilities or learning of English in general. They complained that most of the feedback they received focused on grammatical errors and mechanical issues, such as capitalization and punctuation. Some of the participants criticized the whole learning atmosphere and thought that their teachers treated them as spoiled kids who do not have enough desire to learn. All the participants demanded better feedback quality with timely, clear, and comprehensive comments that offer corrections to their errors and help them improve their writing skills. They asked for student-teacher conferences to elaborate on written comments and maximize the benefit of corrective feedback.

Qutob, M. M., &Madini, A. A. (2020). Saudi EFL Learners' Preferences of the Corrective Feedback on Written Assignment. *English Language Teaching*, 13(2), 16-27.

This is a mixed-method study that examined the preferences of 114 Saudi female EFL learners regarding three different types of corrective feedback on written assignments. The subjects were students at the seventh grade at a private school in Jeddah and their ages ranged from 12 to 13 years old. Data were collected through a closed-ended Likert scale questionnaire and an open-ended question: What correction method do you suggest? Both instruments were given to the subjects after 6 weeks of implementing the experiment. The results showed

that all the subjects thought their teachers' feedback is helpful. There were no major differences in the learners' preferences with respect to the type of corrective feedback desired. The majority of the subjects preferred to receive comprehensive feedback where the teachers point out all their mistakes. Also, they demanded more clear and constructive feedback on how to correct their mistakes. Most of the subjects preferred to receive corrective comments via electronic methods to make feedback more vivid and convenient in addition to the ease of access anywhere and at any time for both learners and teachers.

Rajab, H., Khan, K., &Elyas, T. (2016). A case study of EFL teachers' perceptions and practices in written corrective feedback. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics and English Literature*, 5(1), 119-131.

This is an interpretive exploratory case study that involved 184 EFL teachers (113 females and 71 males) to identify their beliefs and examine their practices regarding Written Corrective Feedback. The participants were randomly selected from 20 higher education institutions throughout Saudi Arabia. The study adopted a mixed-method approach where the participants responded to a 15-question online survey and filled a qualitative data form with an open-ended question. Moreover, The researchers collected additional data through semi-structured interviews with 7 participants (5 males and 2 females). The results revealed the majority of the participants saw WCF as a significant factor to enhance the learners' writing skills and promote in second language acquisition. Many teachers stressed the importance of providing the students with more detailed editing practices to help them become self-aware of their errors. Most of the participants asked for better work conditions with less workload and less students in class to help them elevate their teaching performance. Also, they demanded that their tertiary institutions allocate specified training sessions to help them maximize their abilities to provide quality corrective feedback.

Umer, M., Ahmad, B., &Soomro, A. F. (2018). Saudi Learners' Perceptions of Feedback on Written Tasks. *International Research Journal of Arts & Humanities (IRJAH)*, 46(46), 63-76.

The aim of this study is to investigate the perceptions and preferences of 150 EFL learners towards various methods of corrective feedback for their writing tasks. The subjects were undergraduate students enrolled at the preparatory year, Taif University. The subjects responded to a forty-item questionnaire. The findings indicated that the subjects valued their teachers' written feedback and considered the corrective comments helpful to locate their errors and correct them. Also, the subjects asked for more direct feedback that clarifies the type of error provides tips to avoid the same error in the subsequent writing tasks. They expressed their preferences also to receive comprehensive feedback where all their errors are marked and corrected. This desire to have all kind of errors pointed at and responded to could promote the students' noticing which is a key approach step that makes the process of providing corrective feedback more effective. This preference to see receive more comments on a wide range of errors could make the students pay more attention to different types of grammatical structures and also to other aspects of writing in the target language as well.

References

- Abalkheel, A., & Brandenburg, T. (2020). Effects of Written Corrective Feedback: A Synthesis of 10 Quasi-Experimental Studies. *English Language Teaching*, 13(7), 97-103.
- Abdelrahman, M. A. S. (2016). Teachers' and Students' Preferences for Error Correction in EFL Writing. Doctoral dissertation, Majmaah University, Saudi Arabia.
- Alamri, H. R. H. (2018). Examining the Perceptions and Preferences of Saudi EFL Student Teachers Concerning Teachers' Feedback Practices. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 8(18), 48-67.
- Albelihi, H. H. (2022). Written corrective feedback: A comparative study of the preferences and beliefs of EFL teachers and learners in Saudi Arabia. *F1000Research*, 11, 452-464.
- Albogami, M. (2020). An Inquiry into Effective Written Feedback from EFL Teachers' and Students' Perspectives at a Saudi University. Doctoral dissertation, University of Exeter.
- Alharbi, S. H. (2016). Effect of teachers' written corrective feedback on Saudi EFL University students' writing achievements. *International Journal of Linguistics*, 8(5), 15-29.
- Alharbi, S. H. (2020). Efficacy of different types of written corrective feedback on EFL university students' writing quality. *International Journal of English Linguistics*, 10(4), 217-226.
- Alharthi, S. (2016). Saudi Female Teachers' and Students' Understanding of the Role and the Importance of Feedback on Writing. *Journal of Research in Curriculum Instruction and Educational Technology*, 2(1), 25-43.
- Al-Hazzani, N., &Altalhab, S. (2018). Can Explicit Written Corrective Feedback Develop Grammatical and Lexical Accuracy of Saudi EFL Learners? *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*, 6(4), 16-24.

- Aljasir, N. (2021). Matches or Mismatches? Exploring Shifts in Individuals' Beliefs About Written Corrective Feedback as Students and Teachers-to-be. *Journal of Teaching and Teacher Education*, 9(1), 1-10.
- Alkhatib, N. (2015). Written corrective feedback at a Saudi university: English language teachers' beliefs, students' preferences, and teachers' practices. Doctoral dissertation, University of Essex.
- Alqurashi, F. (2015). Perspectives of Saudi EFL learners towards teacher response in writing courses. *International Journal of English Linguistics*, 5(5), 37-46.
- Al-Saleh, N. A. (2018). The Impact of Positive and Corrective Feedback via Showbie on Saudi Students' English Writing. *Arab World English Journal: Thesis Collection*, 1-121.
- Alshahrani, N. A. (2020). *Learners' Engagement with Written Corrective Feedback and their L2 Writing Performance*. Doctoral dissertation, University of Leicester.
- Alshahrani, A., & Storch, N. (2014). Investigating teachers' written corrective feedback practices in a Saudi EFL context: How do they align with their beliefs, institutional guidelines, and students' preferences? *Australian Review of Applied Linguistics*, 37(2), 101-122.
- Alsharif, A. A., & Alyousef, H. S. (2017). Investigating ESL/EFL students' approaches in response to feedback: A case study. *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 13(2), 153-181.
- Alsuhaibani, Z. (2021). Corrective Feedback Controversies in Language Learning: With a Focus on Direct Written Corrective Feedback. *International Journal of English Language & Translation Studies*, 8(4), 35-43.
- Al-Wossabi, S. A. N. (2019). Corrective feedback in the Saudi EFL writing context: A new perspective. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 9(3), 325-331.
- Alzaharani, H. F. (2016). Teachers' Stated Beliefs on Coded Unfocused Corrective Feedback in EFL Writing at a Saudi University. *TESOL International Journal*, 11(1), 52-64.
- Aseeri, F. M. M. (2019). Written Corrective Feedback as Practiced by Instructors of Writing in English at Najran University. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 8(3), 112-121.
- Basabrin, A. (2019). Exploring EFL instructors and students perceptions of written corrective feedback on blackboard platform: A case study. *Arab World English Journal: Special Issue: Application of Global ELT Practices in Saudi Arabia 1*. 179-192.
- Elboroloso, S. A. (2019). Improving literacy skills of Saudi English Majors through explicit and implicit corrective feedback modes at Shaqra' University. *Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 9(6), 09-16.
- Grami, M. (2004). The Effect of Teachers' Written Feedback on ESL Students' Writing: A Study on a Saudi ESL University-Level Context. Doctoral dissertation, University of Essex.
- Grami, G. M. A., & Alshenqeeti, H. M. A. (2013). Socio-cultural dimension of students' attitudes towards specific forms of corrective feedback: The case of criticism in written comments. *Journal of Teaching and Education*, 2(2), 155-159.
- Halim, T., Wahid, R., & Halim, S. (2021). EFL students' attitudes toward corrective feedback: a study conducted at undergraduate level. *Saudi Journal of Language Studies*, 1(1), 40-49.
- Hamouda, Arafat. (2011). A Study of Students and Teachers' Preferences and Attitudes towards Correction of Classroom Written Errors in Saudi EFL Context. *English Language Teaching* 4(3), 128-141.
- Hussain, M. S., Albeshir, K. B., & Farid, A. (2020). Teachers' Error Treatment Practices and Perceptions in Teaching English to Adult EFL Learners in Saudi Arabia: A Gender-Based Qualitative Study. *Global Regional Review*, 1, 290-299.
- Mustafa, R. F. (2012). Feedback on the Feedback: Sociocultural Interpretation of Saudi ESL Learners' Opinions about Writing Feedback. *English Language Teaching*, 5(3), 3-15.
- Qutob, M. M., & Madini, A. A. (2020). Saudi EFL Learners' Preferences of the Corrective Feedback on Written Assignment. *English Language Teaching*, 13(2), 16-27.
- Rajab, H., Khan, K., & Elyas, T. (2016). A case study of EFL teachers' perceptions and practices in written corrective feedback. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics and English Literature*, 5(1), 119-131.
- Umer, M., Ahmad, B., & Soomro, A. F. (2018). Saudi Learners' Perceptions of Feedback on Written Tasks. *International Research Journal of Arts & Humanities (IRJAH)*, 46(46), 63-76.

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